

DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE ACTIVITIES OF LAW ENFORCEMENT AGENCIES IN THE PREVENTION OF THE CRIME OF HOLDING A PROSTITUTE

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the activities of law enforcement agencies in the field of crime prevention related to the maintenance of brothels. The author assesses the degree of social danger of this crime, its moral and legal consequences, as well as the effectiveness of preventive measures carried out by law enforcement agencies. At the same time, existing problems in crime prevention and proposals for their solution were put forward.

Today, among the factors threatening the spirituality and moral stability of society, the activities of brothels remain one of the most important problems. This vice is inextricably linked not only with moral corruption, but also with other types of crime - human trafficking, violence, the spread of drug addiction.

From this point of view, the fight against the crime of keeping a brothel should not be limited to punitive measures. On the contrary, its prevention and early detection require a systematic approach, especially in the activities of law enforcement agencies.

In practice, there is sufficient evidence that work in this area is not yielding sufficient results. For example, despite the fact that the internal affairs bodies annually suppress the activities of hundreds of brothels, a certain part of them is restored. This situation indicates the ineffectiveness of existing preventive mechanisms.

As Professor B. Nazarov noted:

"Prevention of crime is effective not only through legal measures, but also through the improvement of the socio-moral environment."¹

In the author's opinion, improving the activities of law enforcement agencies in preventing the crime of keeping a brothel is not only an organizational or punitive issue, but also an integral part of social, legal, and spiritual policy.

Therefore, this article, based on scientific analysis, highlights the system for preventing the crime of keeping brothels, problems in the activities of law enforcement agencies, and practical proposals for their elimination.

The fight against the crime of keeping a brothel is not limited to the application of punishment. The legal basis for effective activities in this area is primarily reflected in the Criminal Code, the Criminal Procedure Code, the Code of Administrative Responsibility, the

¹ Nazarov B. Theory and Practice of Crime Prevention. - T.: "Iqtisod-Moliya," 2021. - P. 59.

Law on the Prevention of Crime and Offenses of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and relevant by-laws.

According to Article 131 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the maintenance or organization of a brothel, as well as the creation of conditions for ensuring the activities of such institutions, is considered a crime. This norm provides for such types of punishment as a financial fine or imprisonment as a measure of responsibility for this act.²

At the same time, the Law "On the Prevention of Crime and Offenses" (adopted on May 14, 2014) defines the legal basis for the activities of law enforcement agencies. According to it, one of the priority areas of prevention is the prevention of moral corruption of citizens, the creation of a healthy environment in society.³

• The tasks of internal affairs bodies in this area are clearly defined in the Ministry's regulations and state programs for combating crime. These include:

- early detection of information about the activities of brothels;
- implementation of operational and procedural actions to terminate their activities;
- conducting preventive interviews, control measures, and monitoring work;
- organization of educational work in cooperation with the mahalla, educational institutions, and NGOs.⁴

In addition, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 15, 2022 No. UP-382 defines the tasks of digitalization of the crime prevention system, integration of information databases, and the establishment of operational information exchange. This plays an important role in the detection of hidden crimes, such as brothels.⁵

Although the existing legal framework is sufficiently comprehensive, its effective functioning is directly related to the coordination of the activities of law enforcement agencies and the exchange of information. It is in this aspect that many problems are observed.

In the author's opinion, strengthening cooperation between all entities in the system of combating crime - internal affairs, prosecutor's office, court, and local authorities - is one of the main conditions for preventing the activities of brothels.

Measures aimed at stopping the activities of brothels in practice face a number of obstacles and problems. First of all, the latent nature of these crimes creates serious difficulties for law enforcement agencies. In most cases, such institutions appear to operate legally: for example, massage parlors, "SPA" centers, beauty salons, some hotels, and private houses.⁶

In this case, conducting operational-search activities and collecting evidence is very difficult. For example, according to Article 82 of the Criminal Procedure Code, any investigative action can be carried out only on procedural grounds. However, to turn information about the brothel's activities into official evidence, it is necessary to transfer

² Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Тошкент, 2021. Article 131.

³ Law "On Crime and Crime Prevention." - T.: May 14, 2014. Article 3.

⁴ Regulations of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - T., 2023. - P. 12-15.

⁵ Presidential Decree No. UP-382. "On measures for the digitalization of the system of combating crime." - T.: August 15, 2022.

⁶ Khakimov Sh. Issues of Prevention of Crimes Against Morality. - T.: "Yurist," 2022. - P. 73.

operational information to procedural order - this takes a lot of time and in some cases leads to the loss of evidence.⁷

The second important problem is the lack of a basic evidence base for proving the crime. The activities of a brothel are usually carried out in a closed environment. In such cases, video recordings, witness testimony, or special operational examinations are required. However, in practice, operational-investigative officers are not sufficiently equipped with technical means in this area.⁸

Professor R. Rajabov writes about this:

"The introduction of modern information technologies in the process of detecting and proving crimes should be not only a technical task, but also a conceptual direction of the fight against crime."⁹

In the author's opinion, another shortcoming of the current system is the insufficient exchange of information between law enforcement agencies. The integration of electronic databases between the internal affairs bodies, the prosecutor's office, and the judicial system has not yet been fully established. Therefore, delays and data loss are observed in data exchange.

There are also systemic problems in the mechanism of working with the population in crime prevention. In many cases, preventive conversations are conducted formally, and it is noted that spiritual and educational work among young people and women is not sufficiently effective.

In the author's opinion, in order to improve the system for preventing the activities of brothels:

- strengthening the use of digital technologies in operational-search activities;
- creation of a unified electronic information system between law enforcement agencies;
- preventive work should be carried out in cooperation with the population and NGOs.

The issue of preventing the activities of brothels is a pressing problem not only for Uzbekistan, but also for many countries. Scientists in the field of criminal law and criminology have put forward different approaches in this regard.

According to Professor A. I. Dolgova, the restriction and prevention of brothels should be carried out not only through punishment, but also through the improvement of the spiritual and moral environment in society. He writes:

"The fight against prostitution should be considered not only as a legal measure, but also as a means of social education. State and public organizations must work together in this direction."¹⁰

A similar viewpoint is supported by the Uzbek criminologist S. Mukhtarova. He emphasized that raising public awareness and moral immunity should be the main factor in preventing the activities of brothels.¹¹

At the same time, according to Professor M. K. Tazhikhanov (Kazakhstan), when conducting a scientific analysis of brothels, it is necessary to assess them not only as an object

⁷ Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Тошкент, 2021. Article 82.

⁸ Report of the Ministry of Internal Affairs Information Center. - Т., 2023. - P. 18.

⁹ Rajabov R. Problems of Modern Crime and Cybersecurity. - Тошкент, 2021. - P. 65.

¹⁰ Dolgova A. I. Crime and the morality of society. Moscow: Norma, 2020, p. 118.

¹¹ Mukhtarova S. Gender Aspects of Crime Prevention. - Т.: "Academy of Legal Sciences," 2022. - P. 47.

of crime, but also as a socially dangerous economic system. He emphasized that since the economic aspects of this vice are related to illegal income, tax evasion, and human trafficking, it is necessary to take comprehensive measures against the crime.¹²

- In foreign practice, there are various models in this direction. For example:

- In the Dutch model, prostitution is legalized, but its scope is under strict legal control.

State bodies exercise control through sanitation, taxation, and licensing.

- In the Swedish model, on the contrary, the person who uses the services of prostitution is punished, and the prostitute herself is considered a victim. This approach is aimed at eroding the roots of crime.¹³

- In the Republic of Korea, digital monitoring systems, online platform control, and cyber prevention methods have been implemented to identify brothels. This system contributes to the early detection of crimes.¹⁴

In the author's opinion, foreign experience cannot be fully applied in the conditions of Uzbekistan, but some elements - in particular, digital monitoring, database integration, and public control - can be implemented in the anti-crime system.

From this point of view, scientific discussions show that, along with legal measures, social and moral means of influence are also important in crime prevention. Strengthening cooperation between law enforcement agencies, educational institutions, and NGOs in this area is a requirement of the times.

As can be seen from the above analysis, preventing the activities of brothels is a multifaceted and systematic task for law enforcement agencies. Problems in this area are inextricably linked not only with legal foundations, but also with the social, moral, and spiritual environment.

In the author's opinion, the following proposals and recommendations for the prevention of the crime of keeping a brothel are relevant:

- **Systematic preventive work should be established.**

In the activities of law enforcement agencies, attention should be paid not only to the detection and punishment of crimes, but also to working with citizens, informing the public, and moral prevention.

- **Strengthening the use of digital technologies.**

The activities of brothels are often organized via the Internet, social networks, and closed online platforms. Therefore, it is advisable to create special "cyber-prevention" units within the Ministry of Internal Affairs system.

- **Improvement of information exchange between law enforcement agencies.**

A unified database should be created between the internal affairs bodies, the prosecutor's office, and the judicial system. This increases the possibility of early crime prevention.

- **Expansion of cooperation with the public and NGOs.**

¹² Tajikhanov M. K. *Criminology and problems with prostitution*. - Almaty: Finance and law, 2021. - P. 56.

¹³ Ekberg G. *The Swedish law that prohibits the purchase of sexual services*. – Violence Against Women, 2004. – Vol. 10(10). – P. 1187–1218.

¹⁴ Korean National Police Agency. *Cybercrime and Prostitution Prevention Report*. – Seoul, 2023. – P. 33.

Ensuring the active participation of the mahalla system, women's committees, educational institutions, and civil society institutions will have an effective impact on combating prostitution.

➤ **Use of foreign experience.**

Adapting the elements of digital monitoring and a social approach in the Korean and Swedish experience to local conditions allows for the introduction of new methods of combating crime.

At the same time, the improvement of legislation is of great importance. In particular, it is necessary to revise Article 131 of the Criminal Code, specifying in it cases of financing brothels, providing organizational assistance, and operating through electronic platforms.

Professor B. Ismailov wrote about this:

"In the fight against prostitution and the crimes that constitute it, the goal of the state should be not punishment, but the spiritual cleansing of society and the protection of human dignity."¹⁵

In the author's personal opinion, the most important factor in preventing the activities of brothels is the enhancement of human dignity, strengthening moral immunity, and raising legal culture. Only then will the fight against such vices in society be effective.

¹⁵ Ismoilov B. Society and Spirituality: Legal Analysis. - T.: "Ma'naviyat," 2023. - P. 91.